

Style for IRRN Contributors

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).

- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).

- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.

- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; hot 60 kg/ha N.

- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.

- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.

- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.

- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.

- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

- Type all contributions double-paced. ■

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Performance of rice cultivars on farmers' fields in inland swamps of Sierra Leone

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Rice occupies about 75% of Sierra Leone's cultivated area. Although rice is predominantly in the uplands, the inland-valley swamps contribute a sizable area toward rice production.

To determine the performance of different rice cultivars developed at the Rokupr Rice Research Station on farmers' fields, multilocal tests were conducted under the All Sierra Leone Coordinated Agronomic Trials during

the last four wet seasons. The trials were conducted in all of the districts of Sierra Leone with a fertilizer dose of 40 kg N/ha, 40 kg P₂O₅/ha and 40 kg K₂O/ha. The cultivars ADNY 301, ROK8, and ROK6 produced an average of more than 3.5 t/ha while ROK14 and ROK4 yielded a maximum of 3 to 3.5 t/ha (see table). Besides, ROK6, ROK8, and ADNY 301 are susceptible to a large degree of variation, as much as 2.4 t/ha. The performance of CP4 and ROK5 was almost consistent.

Thus, there is a great scope to increase rice production in Sierra Leone by farmers' adoption of improved rice cultivars such as ADNY 301, ROK8, and ROK6. ■

Range of grain yield (t/ha) of different rice varieties in the inland swamp ecology.

Cultivar	Centers (no.)	Trials (no.)	Yield (t/ha)		
			Lowest	Highest	Difference
RH2	4	16	1.2	2.9	1.7
CP4	5	18	1.8	2.6	0.8
ROK4	3	15	2.3	3.1	0.8
ROK5	4	12	1.8	2.2	0.4
ROK6 (IR5)	6	33	1.1	4.0	2.8
ROK12 (ADNY 11)	4	32	1.1	2.8	1.6
ROK8 (C13H3)	9	48	1.4	3.8	2.4
ADNY 301	7	34	2.0	4.7	2.6
ROK14 (Mange 2)	8	40	1.2	3.2	2.0

TKM9 — An improved red rice variety

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TKM9 is a red-rice derivative of the cross TKM7 (a pure line selection from Kullakar) and IR8. Developed at

Tirurkuppam, TKM9 is a high yielding semidwarf with short bold grain that matures in 110 days under wetland conditions. It is moderately resistant to fulgorids, leaf folders, sheath rot, tungro, and bacterial blight.

TKM9 can be grown like ragi *Eleusine coracana* with limited irrigation. Able to withstand drought, it can also be grown in dryland and semidryland

Performance of TKM9 at Tirurkuppam, Tamil Nadu, India

Variety	Wetland yield (t/ha)	Yield increase over IR20 (%)	Yield (t/ha) with limited irrigation	Increase or decrease (%) compared with CO34
TKM9	5.2	44.4	2.9	81
ADT31	4.3	19.4	1.9	19
CO34	4.1	13.9	1.6	—
IR20	3.6	—	0.7	56